

BUSINESS DISCOURSE AS AN INSTITUTIONAL REALITY

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Abstract:

The article is dedicated to defining the concept of discourse and business discourse, which is a type of institutional discourse and has a purposeful status-role speech. The article will also present the rules of business etiquette, the need for its knowledge and the characteristics of the institutionalization of business discourse.

Keywords: Discourse, Institutional Discourse, Business Discourse, Business Etiquette.

Introduction:In the age of globalization and information technology, business discourse is a key tool for the development of international business, because it is international business communications that play a special role in the effective and successful business of states, international organizations, transnational corporations, individuals and legal entities. International business relations provide the perception and understanding of the cultural traditions and values of different countries of the world, the effective use and management of international etiquette, ethical norms, integrated marketing communications. Business discourse is becoming increasingly popular as a topical area of research.

Discourse Overview I

The existence of discourse theory is increasingly felt in linguistics. Before moving directly to business discourse, let me briefly review the discourse. It should be noted that the development of the theory of discourse is related to the names of such scholars as E. Benveniste, U. Maas, M. Foucault, Z. Harris, E.S. Kubriakova, A. Kudlaeva, T. A. Van Dijk, N.D. Arutinova and many other scientists. The development of the theory of discourse in linguistics dates back to the 60s of the twentieth century.

Z. Harris, in his 1952 article entitled Discourse Analysis, explained discourse as a simple combination of phrases with continuous narration. The linguist of that era only considers language from a sentence level. Harris writes a broader analysis of language that does not dwell on the internal linguistic (sentence) level, but rather explores the connection between the text and the context.

U. Maas defines discourse as an appropriate linguistic formation in relation to socially and historically defined social practices [27, 204].

N. D. Arutinova defines discourse as speech, which is considered as a purposeful social action, as a component involved in the interaction of people and their mechanisms of consciousness, cognitive processes, this is speech "Hidden in Life" [1, p. 136-137].

T. A. Van Dijk defines discourse as a communication event that takes place between the speaker and the listener (observer, etc.), the process of communicative action takes place in the context of a certain time and space [8, 312].

There are various definitions of discourse in the linguistic literature. This is because discourse is a complex phenomenon: it is much more than a word, a sentence, a text, what is said. However, these are also components of discourse and without them there is no discourse.

V.I. Karasik distinguishes two main types of discourse: personal (person-centered) and institutional (status-oriented). In the first case the speaker appears as a person, with all his inner nature. In the second case - as a representative of a certain social institution (Karasik, 2000: 8). Participants in personal discourse know each other well, the speaker acts as an individual, while in institutional discourse he / she is "The communicative speech of the

representatives of social groups or institutions with each other, with people who are aware of the possibilities of their status-role. They have established a framework of social institutions, which is determined by the needs of society at a particular stage of its development "[4, p.280]. A key feature of institutional discourse is its involvement in social interaction, which takes place mainly within public institutions.

Institutional Discourse II

Institutional Discourse (English: Institutional Discourse, French: discours Institutionnel, German: Institutieller Diskurs) is communication in the established social institutions of society [T. A. Van Dijk, 2008].

In some linguistic works, the concept of "institutional discourse" is understood as "discourse produced in social institutions that involves communication as an integral part of their organization" [S Siegel, 2000, p. 43].

It is "specialized clichéd communication between people who may not have known each other personally, but should communicate in accordance with the regulations of that society" [Karasik, 2002, p. 292].

Any institutional discourse uses a certain system of professionally oriented signs or, in other words, has its own subtext (special vocabulary, phraseology) [24, 368]. A person enters a particular discourse space not only for a certain social role (including or implying the type of social institution), but also for certain purposes. Institutional discourse is a very broad concept that includes both the language system (the part of it that is specifically focused on a given section of communications), as well as speech activity (a combination of linguistic and extralinguistic factors) and text.

Institutional discourse is the communication of status-role relationships within a given framework [9, 14]. In modern society there are the following types of institutional discourse: political, diplomatic, administrative, legal, military, pedagogical, religious, mystical, medical, business, advertising, sports, scientific, scenic and mass information (mass media). Institutional discourse is distinguished by two systemic characteristics: goals and participants in communication [9, 15]. For example, the goal of political discourse is to seize and maintain power, pedagogical discourse is the socialization of a new member of society, business discourse is the establishment of mutually beneficial business relationships between organizations, and so on. The main participants in the institutional discourse are the representatives of a particular institution and the people who address them.

Thus, institutional communication is communication through a kind of mask [3, 66]. It is a stereotypical communication that fundamentally distinguishes institutional discourse from personal. The specifics of institutional discourse are revealed in its type, i.e. The type of public institution, which is defined by a special name in the collective linguistic consciousness, that is generalized in the basic concept of this institution (political discourse - power, pedagogical - teaching, religious - faith, legal - law, medical - health, etc.), It is related to certain functions of people, structures built to perform these functions, social rituals and stereotypes of behavior, as well as to the texts created in this social formation [5, 77].

Business discourse III

One of the interesting types and directions of institutional discourse is business discourse, which is characterized by institutional and cognitive-linguistic features and which distinguishes it from other types of discourse. This is to follow the rules of business communication. It manifests itself in defining the basic concepts of business culture, professionally managed ideas and concepts, norms of institutional and personal behavior.

According to A. Stebletsova, business discourse is a universal type of institutional discourse that provides the necessary level of communication interaction in any field of professional activity (Stebletsova, 2014).

According to Francesca Bargiela-Chiapini and Nickerson, Business discourse is verbal or written communication between people who are directly interested in business interactions to support their own interests (or the interests of their organization), while communicators are holders of specific status role relationships (Bargiela - Chiappini and Nickerson 2002).

It should be noted that business communication can be understood as any kind of communication between partners, which is aimed at resolving certain business issues and has an interpersonal character (Imametdinova 1996).

I find Shiriaeva's point of view quite interesting: He primarily understands business discourse as a person with purposeful verbal status and role activity; And business relationships, which are aimed at making a profit and are based on the rules and regulations adopted in the communication of the business community, which is their common feature (Shiriaeva 2014)

These definitions provide a visual representation of the status role (institutional) characteristics of business discourse, as well as its important quality, such as universality. Business discourse has been studied as a subtype of institutional discourse [5, p. 286];

For business discourse, not only special vocabulary is used, but also discursive formulas - special functionally defined speech flows that are characteristic of communication in a particular social institution (in this case, it is a business institution) [8, p. 10].

D. Naumenko, considers English-language business discourse as a kind of institutional discourse, which serves the professional community of business entities and clients, organized basic concepts BUSY (active, busy), ENTERPRISE (entrepreneurship), MANAGE (management), MARKET (market), PROFIT (profit), combined in the macro concept BUSINESS - business.

Business discourse basically includes two aspects that serve to establish communication for business purposes using different means in different contexts. The first is mentioned, as a spoken business discourse and reflected in business meetings, interviews, presentations, etc. And the second is known as written discourse and consists of emails, faxes, letters, business reports, and so on.

Institutional business discourse is a purposeful status role speech of people, which is a common feature of business relationships (production of goods, financing this production, issuance of cash loans, Insurance, trade, sales of products and various services, e.g. as goods registration, distribution and repair, purchase of goods or services, sale, preliminary negotiations on this type of business relationship), which includes not only internal organizations, but also communications between organizations as well as communication between organizations and individuals. Adherence to the norms and rules of communication is accepted in the business community [23.50].

Business etiquette IV

Ethics is an important part of communication culture. Thus, norms of behavior based on moral and ethical principles. There are various professional ethics available today. For example: journalism ethics, business ethics, doctor ethics and more. The key to modern business is successful negotiation and bargaining. In business communication, the interlocutors must follow the rules of business etiquette, otherwise the parties will not be able to reach an agreement. Rules of business etiquette are a combination of written and oral rules of conduct. We are taught the rules of behavior from childhood, these are more social rules of behavior. We have mastered them so that we can complete them automatically. By using the

same rules we can show respect to those around us. The rules of business etiquette are an extension of the same principles. Respect the people you have a relationship with at work.

It is the source of your success. Knowledge of business etiquette is essential for running a successful business. Knowledge of business etiquette can improve teamwork, relationship with partners, productivity and customer satisfaction.

Adherence to etiquette and ethics in business communication is a kind of "packaging" of a product called information. The better packaged the goods, the more attractive it is, therefore the more valuable it is. Within the communicating in business, when we want to reach some kind of agreement with someone each type of information needs to be conveyed as efficiently as possible, for which we need to use universally recognized norms of ethics and etiquette.

Institutional business relations - is the communication, It is the exchange of important information for the participants of the business relationship (between business entities). In order to achieve effective communication, it is necessary to clarify the following issues:

- What are the means of communication and how to use them properly in the process of business relations;
- How to overcome the barriers of misunderstanding and make communication successful.

The role and importance of communication in international business is great and it is constantly evolving.

The characteristics of business discourse institutionalization are:

a specific purpose of communication;
specific participants;
a specific social chronotop;
specific values;
specific strategies;
a specific overall picture of the world;
specific characteristics of texts (Shiryaeva 2014).

Features of formal business discourse include stability, standardization, because its field of application is business relations between people, institutions and states. Whereas official business discourse is characterized by strict accuracy, objectivity, specificity, conciseness, lack of imagery and emotionality; Then its choice of means is determined by the same characteristics. In particular, the use of international lexical items will not be dictated by a desire to implement a basic pragmatic attitude, as content expressed in a formal business style should exclude the possibility of ambiguity and inconsistency.

Conclusion

Thus, we can conclude that business discourse with "institutional universality", the purposefulness of speech behavior and the correlation of the business picture of the world, as a key parameter of interaction between communicators, has a clearly defined cultural and communicative orientation, as well as a characteristic pragmatic-semantic loading and stylistic regulation. Business discourse is a format of communication between individuals in which business relationships act as a common parameter; They are based on a common perception and understanding of the world business picture, a combination of professional values and knowledge, the most important principles of speech etiquette.

References

1. Арутюнова Н. Д. Дискурс [Текст] // Линг-1. вистический энциклопедический словарь. – М. : Советская энциклопедия, 1990. – С. 136–137.
2. Бенвенист, Э. Формальный аппарат высказывания [Текст]/ Э. Бенвенист. Общая лингвистика. М., 1974. –447 с.
.Дейк, Т.А. Ван Язык. Познание. Коммуникация [Текст]/Т. А. Ван Дейк. Пер. с англ. – М.: Прогресс, 1989. –412 с.
4. Карасик В. И. Языковые ключи [Текст]: 4. моногр. / В.И. Карасик. – Волгоград : Парадигма, 2007. – 520 с.
5. Карасик В. И. Языковой круг : личность, 5. концепты, дискурс [Текст] : моногр. / В.И. Карасик. – Волгоград : Перемена, 2002. – 477 с.
6. Карасик В. И. Этнокультурные типы институционального дискурса // Этнокультурная специфика речевой деятельности: сб. обзоров. – М. : ИНИОН РАН, 2000. – С. 37–64.
7. Карасик, В. И. Языковая матрица культуры / В. И. Карасик. – М. : Гнозис, 2013. – 320 с.
7. Крысин, Л.П. Социолингвистические аспекты изучения современного русского языка [Текст] / Л.П. Крысин М., 1989.
8. Кубрякова, Е.С., Александрова, О.В. Виды пространств текста и дискурса. [Текст]/ Е.С.
9. Кубрякова, О.В. Алек-андрова. Категоризация мира: пространство и время. Материалы научной конференции. М., 1997.
10. Кудлаева, А.Н. Типы текстов в структуре дискурса. Дисс. на соискание учен. степени канд. филол. наук. [Текст]/ А.Н. Кудлаева. Пермь, 2006.
11. Науменко Л. П.10. Діловий англомовний дискурс у ключових концептах [Текст] // Культура народов Причерноморья. – 2004. – Т. 1. – № 49. – С. 40 – 44.
12. Naumenko, L. (2012) Criterii Vydilennia Kliu-chovykh Kontseptiv Suchasного Anglomovного Business-Dyskursu. Part 1. Movny ta Konstseptualny Kartyny Svitу 42,197–205
(1) (PDF) The subordinate concept ‘marketing’ in the contemporary business English discourse. Available from:https://www.researchgate.net/publication/277886629_The_subordinate_concept_'marketing'_in_the_contemporary_business_English_discourse [accessed Apr 08 2022].
13. Стеблецова, А. О. Национальная специфика делового дискурса в сфере высшего образования (на материале англоязычной и русскоязычной письменной коммуникации) : автореф. дис. ... д-ра филол. наук / Стеблецова Анна Олеговна. – Воронеж, 2015. – 44 с.
14. Фуко, М. Порядок дискурса [Текст] /М. Фуко. Воля к истине. М., 1996.
15. Шевченко І. С. Дискурс як мисленнєво-12. комунікативна діяльність [Текст] / І. С. Шевченко, О. І. Морозова // Дискурс як когнітивно-комунікативний феномен. – Харків : Константа, 2005. – С. 21-29.
16. Шевченко І. С. Когнітивно-прагматичні 13. дослідження дискурсу [Текст] // Дискурс як когнітивно-комунікативний феномен. – Харків : Константа, 2005. – С. 105-118.
17. Шейгал Е. И. Семиотика политического дискурса. – М. : Гнозис, 2004. – 324 с.
18. Ширяева, Т.А. К вопросу о статусе дискурса [Текст] / Т.А. Ширяева. Вестник ПГЛУ.-2006. – 49–55 с.

1. Brown, P. (2015). Politeness and language. In J. Wright (Ed.), *The international encyclopedia of the social and behavioral sciences* (pp. 326–330). Elsevier. <https://doi.org/10.1016/B978-0-08-097086-8.53072-4>
2. Brown, P., & Levinson, S. C. (1987). *Politeness: Some universals in language usage* (Vol. 4). Cambridge University Press. <https://doi.org/10.1017/CBO9780511813085>
3. Burkhardt, A. (Ed.). (2010). *Speech acts, meaning and intentions: Critical approaches to the philosophy of John R. Searle*. Walter de Gruyter.
4. Bargiela-Chiappini F., Harris S. *The Language of Business: An International Perspective*. – Edinburgh : Edinburgh University Press, 1997. – 386 p.
5. Bargiela-Chiappini F., Nickerson C., Planken B. *Business Discourse*. – London : Palgrave Macmillan, 2007. – 282 p.
6. Bargiela-Chiappini, F. Introduction: Business Discourse / F. Bargiela-Chiappini // *The Handbook of Business Discourse* / ed. by F. Bargiela-Chiappini. – Edinburgh : Edinburgh University Press, 2009. – P. 1–18.
7. Imametdinova, R.H. (1996). Delovaya kommunikaciya v promyshlennom [Business communication in industry]. *Gornyj informacionno-analiticheskij byulleten' (nauchno-tekhnicheskij zhurnal)*, (2), 74-75.
8. Kitamura, N. (2000). Adapting Brown and Levinson's "Politeness" theory to the analysis of casual conversation (pp. 163–169). In *Proceedings of ALS2k, the 2000 Conference of the Australian Linguistic Society*. Melbourne: University of Melbourne
9. Maas U. *Als der Geist der Gemeinschaft eine Sprache fand. Sprache im Nationalsozialismus*. Opladen, 1984.
10. Trevino, L. K., & Nelson, K. A. (2016). *Managing business ethics: Straight talk about how to do it right*. John Wiley & Sons.
11. VAN DIJK, T.A. (ed.) 2007. *Discourse Studies. Sage Benchmarks in Discourse Studies*. London, Sage, 5 vols